

EBFMC25-OP-78 · The Knowledge, Attitudes, and Practices of Family Physicians Regarding Adult Vaccination

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15824460>

Oral Presentation #78 was presented at the 3rd International Eastern Black Sea Family Medicine Congress, held in Ordu, Türkiye, on May 22–24, 2025, and is part of the proceedings titled: *Proceedings of the 3rd International Eastern Black Sea Family Medicine Congress*.

AUTHORS

Mahcube Cubukcu
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4799-6848>

Erdogan Semiz
<https://orcid.org/0009-0002-4700-0107>

AFFILIATIONS

Samsun University, Faculty of Medicine
Department of Family Medicine
Samsun, Turkey

Samsun University, Faculty of Medicine
Department of Family Medicine
Samsun, Turkey

ABSTRACT

Introduction: The recommendations of family physicians, who are the primary physicians for preventive and therapeutic adult health, play an important role in the attitudes and behaviors of patients regarding vaccination. This study aimed to contribute to the increase in adult vaccination rates by examining the knowledge, attitudes, and behaviors of family physicians.

Materials and Methods: This research is a cross-sectional, observational, and descriptive survey study. Data were collected using a questionnaire form using a face-to-face survey method. The SPSS 26.0 package program was used for the data. Kolmogorov-Smirnov test, Chi-Square Test, Mann-Whitney U test, Kruskal-Wallis test, and Games-Howell test were used in the statistical analysis of the data.

Results: The average age of the participating physicians was 46, 35.7% were female, 64.3% were male, 88.4% were married, 31.7% had chronic diseases, 70% were general practitioners, an average of 20 years of experience in the profession and an average of 11 years of experience in family medicine. Among the adult vaccines that physicians know the most, 87.9% diphtheria-tetanus, 83.4% influenza, 72.9% COVID-19, 94% Hepatitis A, and 89.4% Hepatitis B stand out, while 19.1% chickenpox, 29.1% shingles, and 29.6% MMR vaccines are less known. While 90% of the participants used sources, 84.42% Ministry of Health (asi.gov.tr), 24.1% EKMUD guide, and 5.03% CDC guides were cited as sources. Half of the physicians sometimes recommend and question vaccines to patients. It is seen that their attitudes towards information about vaccines are quite positive. One third of the participants have received in-service training and prefer inservice training and scientific meetings to access up-to-date information. Hepatitis A vaccine is the least known reimbursable vaccine. The study found that physicians did not fully vaccinate with the recommended vaccines, and the rate of influenza vaccination, especially in the 2023-2024 season, was 40%. 97% of the participants had been vaccinated as adults, 86.4% of whom had received the Tetanus-diphtheria vaccine, 85.4% the COVID-19 vaccine, 59.3% the influenza vaccine, and 57.3% the hepatitis B vaccine.

Conclusion: Increasing the knowledge and awareness of family physicians through in-service training and scientific meetings on adult vaccination will also increase vaccination recommendations. Vaccination for healthcare professionals should also be completed according to the guidelines. Integrating adult vaccination guidelines into warning systems in a way that physicians can most easily use will increase awareness.

PEER REVIEW STATEMENT

This paper has undergone a double-blind peer review process and has been approved by the scientific committee of the conference.

KEYWORDS

Adult vaccination, family medicine, knowledge, lifelong immunization, vaccine preventable diseases

INTRODUCTION

Immunization represents a cornerstone of global public health, preventing millions of deaths annually. Vaccines stimulate the body's immune system to recognize and combat pathogens, significantly reducing the risk of infectious disease. Upon administration, a vaccine elicits an adaptive immune response, facilitating immunological memory and long-term protection (Jones, 2024). The COVID-19 pandemic placed immense strain on health systems and led to significant disruptions. The most recent data on DTP (diphtheria-tetanus-pertussis) immunization coverage underscores the ongoing need for catch-up efforts, recovery, and system strengthening. Although immunization is one of the most successful public health interventions, global coverage had stagnated in the decade preceding COVID-19. The pandemic and its associated disruptions severely challenged immunization efforts in 2020 and 2021. Data from 2023 indicate that performance has not yet returned to pre-pandemic levels seen in 2019 (Barqawi 2024). Childhood immunizations are routinely included in standard healthcare services worldwide and are successfully implemented through structured programs. While significant reductions in vaccine-preventable diseases have been observed among children, immunization in adults—and the associated morbidity and mortality from infectious diseases—continues to be overlooked. Unlike children, adults often lack structured vaccination programs. Even in developed Western countries, adult immunization coverage remains below targeted levels. Consequently, adults still die from diseases that are preventable by vaccination. Family physicians, who serve as primary care providers in both preventive and therapeutic aspects of adult health, play a crucial role in shaping patients' attitudes and behaviors toward vaccination through their recommendations. This study aims to collaborate with family physicians, who are central to preventive healthcare, to generate data at the primary care level that could contribute to structured programs, with the ultimate goal of raising adult immunization rates to levels comparable to those of childhood vaccinations. The increase in childhood immunizations under the Expanded Program on Immunization (EPI) has led to a reduction in the incidence of vaccine-preventable diseases; however, it has also resulted in a rise in case numbers among adolescents and adults. This increase can be attributed to factors such as waning immunity over time, lack of booster doses, and the presence of individuals with incomplete vaccination. As a result, adolescents, adults, and the elderly are at higher risk for these diseases (Toprak, 2018). Immunization practices highlight the importance of high vaccination coverage within the target population. Even in developed countries, low vaccination coverage rates among adults and the elderly contribute to the continued circulation of infectious agents and increase the risk of infection among susceptible individuals. Therefore, increasing vaccination rates among adults and the elderly is essential for their protection. Adult and elderly immunization efforts often focus solely on high-risk groups, which is insufficient for achieving herd immunity. For this reason, adopting a 'Life-Course Immunization' approach, restructuring immunization programs to cover the entire lifespan, and delivering these services through primary healthcare institutions are of great importance (Uzuner, 2018).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted face-to-face with 199 family physicians between June 15 and August 15, 2024. The study population consisted of 423 family physicians actively working in Family Health Centers (FHCs) in Samsun Province as of April 2024, including 152 women and 271 men. The sample size was calculated using the OpenEpi program, with a 5% margin of error and 95% confidence interval, resulting in a target sample size of 193 physicians.

The data were collected using a questionnaire titled 'Assessment of Knowledge, Attitudes, and Practices of Family Physicians Working in Family Health Centers in Samsun Regarding Adult Vaccination.' The questionnaire included 44 questions. The first 9 questions assessed sociodemographic characteristics. The subsequent questions focused on the physicians' perspectives on the necessity of recommending vaccines to adults, frequency of inquiring about adult vaccination status during outpatient visits, frequency of recommending vaccines to adults, vaccines administered in FHCs, vaccines included in the adult immunization program, self-assessed sufficiency of knowledge regarding adult immunization, awareness of the existence of an adult immunization guide, status of receiving in-service training on adult immunization, difficulties in accessing up-to-date information, preferred sources for current information on adult immunization, and knowledge about adult vaccines reimbursed by the Social Security Institution (SGK). Only family physicians actively working in FHCs during the specified dates were included in the study.

This research project was approved by the Samsun University Non-Interventional Clinical Research Ethics Committee on 28.11.2023, with the decision number 2024/08/05.

RESULTS

Immunization practices highlight the importance of achieving high vaccination coverage within the target population. Even in developed countries, low vaccination coverage rates among adults and the elderly contribute to the continued circulation of infectious agents and increase the risk of infection among susceptible individuals. Therefore, increasing vaccination rates among adults and the elderly is essential for their protection. Adult and elderly immunization efforts often focus solely on high-risk groups, which is insufficient for achieving herd immunity. For this reason, adopting a 'Life-Course Immunization' approach, restructuring immunization programs to cover the entire lifespan, and delivering these services through primary healthcare institutions are of great importance."

The vaccines most commonly recognized by physicians as adult vaccines were diphtheria-tetanus, influenza, COVID-19, hepatitis A, and hepatitis B. Only 10% of the participating physicians stated that they did not use any information source. Although the rate of resource use has increased compared to previous years, it can be suggested that the effective use of resources would benefit from updated information being regularly delivered to each family physician via medical associations or public health directorates, or by integrating it into the software they use, thus ensuring continuous updates. Approximately one-third of the participating physicians reported having received in-service training on adult immunization. The rate of recommending vaccines to high-risk groups was generally low among the family physicians in our study. The most frequently recommended vaccines were hepatitis B, pneumococcal, and influenza vaccines. It can be stated that increased follow-up of patients with chronic diseases, improved access to vaccine-preventable disease serology through laboratories, the absence of vaccine supply issues, and the reduction of barriers to adult vaccination will contribute to higher vaccine recommendation rates.

DISCUSSION

Preventive measures that begin at every stage of life and continue throughout the lifespan have gained increasing importance due to the aging of the global population. The concept of 'healthy aging' not only includes balanced nutrition and regular physical activity, but also encompasses the reduction of infectious diseases and their potential complications through vaccination. Therefore, increasing adult immunization rates is of critical importance. The strengths of this study include its implementation with primary care physicians, specifically family physicians who play a central role in immunization, and its distribution across the entire province. The study's limitations include the inability to reach a larger number of participants and the relatively high number of survey questions.

CONCLUSION

The majority of participating family physicians stated that the biggest barrier to vaccination is the patients' lack of knowledge about vaccines. They also considered patients' refusal of vaccines or their belief that they do not need them as obstacles and reported that patients have concerns regarding the safety of vaccines.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

We thank all participants.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST DECLARATION

There is no conflict of interest.

REFERENCES

Barqawi, H. J., Samara, K. A., Haddad, E. S., Bakkour, L. M., & Amawi, F. B. (2024). Attitudes and practices to adult vaccination among physicians before and after COVID-19 pandemic in the United Arab Emirates. *Vaccine: X*, 17, 100455.

Jones, C. H., Jenkins, M. P., & Williams, B. A. (2024). Exploring the future adult vaccine landscape—Crowded schedules and new dynamics. *NPJ Vaccines*, 9(1), 24.

Toprak, D., Koksall, I., Sargin, M., & Akan, H. (2018). Adult vaccination, problems in practice and solution proposals, role of family physicians in adult vaccination. *Turkish Journal of Family Practice*, 22(3), 166–174.

Uzuner, A., Arabacı, Ş., Yüceel, A. İ., Kocatürk, A. C., Kaynar, E., & Khan, A. (2018). Knowledge, attitude and behaviors of adults about adulthood immunization. *Turkish Journal of Family Medicine and Primary Care*, 12(3), 218–225. <https://doi.org/10.21763/tjfmpc.452487>

CORRESPONDING AUTHOR

Mahcube Cubukcu

Samsun University, Faculty of Medicine

Department of Family Medicine

Samsun, Turkey

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4799-6848>

mahcube@gmail.com